

Social Security on the Employee Performance of Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State

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The study evaluated the social security on the employee performance of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to; evaluate the effect of health insurance on the employee output; influence of profit sharing on the employee punctuality and the influence of paid leaves on the employee retention. The study firms were: Nigerian Breweries, Aqua Raph Investment and Juhel company, Descriptive survey design approach was adopted. A total population of 2668 selected staff of the study firms. Sample size of three hundred and thirty-six (336) using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error was adopted. Three hundred and one (301) staff returned the questionnaire. Data was presented and analysed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analysed using Z – test statistic tool. The study revealed that Health insurance had positive effect on the employee output, $Z(95, n = 301) = 8.415 < 11.643, p < .05$; Profit sharing had positive effect on punctuality of the employees, $Z(95, n = 301) = 7.190 < 8.689, p < .05$ and Paid leaves had positive effect on the employee retention of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, $Z(95, n = 301) = 8.415 < 11.643, p < .05$. The study concluded that social security had positive effect employee performance of the firms in Enugu State. The study recommended that the manufacturing firms should offer health insurance as part of their employee benefits package to enhance and attract more qualified workers.

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ABSTRACT

Keywords: Social Security; Employee Performance; Profit-sharing; Health Insurance; Employee Retention; Tobacco Manufacturing Firms

Introduction

Human resources, as a company's driving power, are a pivotal point in its growth that requires constant attention from management (Gunawan, Ilyas and Naninsih, 2017; Saputra, 2017). The attention of the firm must be organized and programmed (Anggraeni, 2015). The existence of a labour social security program, which serves as a type of labour rights protection, might represent the company's care or concern for its employees (Zein, 2016). The term "social security" refers to the government system in a nation that is dedicated to providing social security services (Larimore, 2019). Workers are protected by labour social security in the form of monetary compensation in lieu of a portion of lost or decreased income and services as a result of events or conditions such as workplace accidents, sickness, pregnancy, maternity, old age, and death (Gunawan et. al, 2017). The overall goal of social security is to provide employment security for people while also increasing overall productivity through improved performance.

Organizations can implement a variety of social security strategies to improve worker performance. Health insurance, profit sharing in the workplace, and paid leave for employees are all examples of social security policies that may be implemented in the workplace. A contract requiring an insurer to pay some or all of a person's healthcare bills in exchange for a premium is known as health insurance (Kaynack, 2021). In South Africa, health insurance (also known as medical aid) is a form of insurance that covers all or part of the risk of a person incurring medical bills. The main purpose of health insurance is to prevent employees from incurring out-of-pocket medical expenses, which can be rather costly, especially in a nation like Nigeria.

Profit sharing, for example, is a technique that may assist incentivize employees while also boosting their performance. Paid leaves are also a good approach to improve worker performance as a social security strategy. In addition to employees' normal salaries and bonuses, profit sharing refers to different incentive systems implemented by firms that give direct or indirect rewards to employees based on the company's profitability (Kenton, 2021). Paid leave, on the other hand, refers to time away from work for which an employee is compensated, and is restricted to sick time, vacation time, compensatory time, and leave delivered as a lump sum for usage by the employee for any of these same purposes (Law Insider Dictionary, 2022). Putting all of these in place increases the likelihood of great staff performance in food, beverage, and tobacco production companies, owing to the amount of incentive it generates.

Employees are also the wheels that propel the company vehicle forward. Employees are the lifeblood of every company. This is one of the primary motivators for businesses to seek out methods to improve employee performance. Employee performance refers to a scenario in which an employee or workers are deeply rooted and devoted to their jobs and the organizations for which they work. It is a good treatment for organizational growth since it builds a strong positive relationship between the company and its personnel. Employee performance also encourages employees to be excited about their jobs, which benefits the company's reputation and interests (Kahn, 2014). As a result, employee performance is critical in all businesses, both public and private, including social security institutions, because workers play critical roles in serving the public and ensuring social security service provisions, such as pension and provident schemes (McKay, 2018). Furthermore, when employees are aware of some type of social security, their performance is bound to increase.

Furthermore, employee effectiveness in the workplace promotes productivity because employee(s) who are both passionate and deeply rooted in good attitudes. Generally, attitudes toward the company and its principles are extremely fruitful.

This is advantageous to the company since it ensures a more pleasant relationship between the company and its employees. Organizations often try to advance via productivity, which entails achieving certain goals and objectives (Mlay, 2020). Employee performance is correctly reflected in their production, which is also influenced by the timeliness and regularity of the chehal chehaliers. High output equals high efficiency. The three essential components from which the study aims to interpret employee performance are output, timeliness, and staff retention.

Employee performance enhances overall organizational productivity, which companies rely on to meet their varied goals throughout the year. This indicates that it is in the best interests of Enugu State's food, beverage, and tobacco companies to give social security to their workers in order to boost their performance. In light of this, the study

looked at the impact of social security on employee performance in Enugu State's food, beverage, and tobacco manufacturing firms.

Statement of the Problem

In an ideal society, workers' well-being would be paramount. This is the primary goal of creating social security systems across the world. This is to provide workers with a backup plan in the event that they retire or become ill at work. Employees' performance is improved by social security systems, which ensure that a portion of their supposedly earned money is placed aside for future goals or retirement. Social security might take several forms, including providing health insurance to employees, profit sharing within the company, and paid leave for employees. All of this is geared at enhancing employee performance, increasing employee timeliness, and retaining staff when feasible.

There is, however, a significant gap between what is and what is ideal. Employee wellness should be prioritized in the ideal circumstance. However, without a comprehensive social security system, health insurance systems will be difficult to construct, and paid leaves and profit sharing will be impossible. Many manufacturing companies in Enugu State are in this situation. These businesses do not provide health insurance to its employees. Even in Nigeria as a whole, just a tiny percentage of the population participates in the National Health Insurance Scheme. Paid absences are also being phased out in an effort to save money and utilize organizational resources. Employers push nursing moms to take unpaid absences in order to increase their earnings. In this section of the world, profit sharing is also not prevalent.

All of these difficulties lead to the organization's overall productivity and performance measurements declining. Employee production is declining, and employees are less driven to improve their timeliness. Some may even go for new jobs that would provide them with a higher degree of worry and social security. The study looked at the impact of social security on employee performance in food, beverage, and tobacco manufacturing enterprises in Enugu State in light of these issues and potential remedies.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the social security and employee performance of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to;

- i. Evaluate the effect of health insurance on the employee output of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State.
- ii. Examine the influence of profit sharing on the punctuality of the employees of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State.
- iii. Assess the influence of paid leaves on the employee retention of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

- i. What is the effect of health insurance on the employee output of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State?
- ii. What is the effect of profit sharing on the punctuality of the employees of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State?
- iii. What is the effect of paid leaves on the employee retention of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study;

- i. Health insurance has no positive effect on the employee output of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State.
- ii. Profit sharing has no positive effect on the punctuality of the employees of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

- iii. Paid leaves have no positive effect on the employee retention of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Significance of the Study

The study looked at the impact of social security on employee performance in Enugu State's food, beverage, and tobacco manufacturing companies. The findings will be useful to state manufacturing company executives, employees, and the state government. The study will be useful to managers because it will show how putting in place social security procedures may assist improve employee performance in an Enugu manufacturing sector. The research will also assist employees in understanding the value of social security and how to demand it from the various firms where they seek employment. The government may learn from this in terms of establishing social security for its employees and ensuring that businesses implement it.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Social Security

The government system in a nation that provides social security services is known as social security (Larimore, 2019). The services vary depending on the country's level of development and economy; for example, in developed countries, monetary services are provided to people with insufficient income or no income at all, as well as those in the formal sector with deductions and benefits who have been contributing to the respective social security entities for their retirement benefits (Gruber and Wise, 1999). However, in most developing nations, services cater primarily to those in formal employment, while benefits are typically low, with a large population in the informal sector unable to access social security services (Bach, 2003).

Components of Social Security

The following are components of social security reviewed in the study.

Health Insurance

A contract requiring an insurer to pay some or all of a person's healthcare bills in exchange for a premium is known as health insurance. More precisely, health insurance often covers the insured's medical, surgical, prescription medication, and dental expenditures. Health insurance can pay the care provider directly or compensate the insured for expenditures incurred due to illness or accident. It is frequently included in employer benefit packages as a method of attracting top talent, with premiums partially funded by the company but frequently withheld from employee paychecks. With limited exclusions for S company workers, the cost of health insurance premiums is deductible to the payer, and the benefits received are tax-free (Kagan, 2021).

Profit Sharing

In addition to employees' normal salaries and bonuses, profit sharing refers to different incentive systems implemented by firms that give direct or indirect rewards to employees based on the company's profitability. In publicly listed corporations, these schemes usually consist of stock distribution to employees (Dean, 2015). Theodore Cooke Taylor, an English woollen mill owner in the late 1800s, is said to have been one of the first to implement profit sharing at his mills. Profit-sharing plans are based on established economic sharing principles that specify how profits are distributed between the corporation as a principal and the employee as an agent.

Paid Leave

Paid leave refers to time off work for which an employee is compensated, and includes but is not limited to sick time, vacation time, compensatory time, and leave granted in an aggregate sum for use by the employee for any of these same purposes. Paid short- or long-term disability, catastrophic leave, and other comparable benefits are not included in "paid leave." Workers may be unable or unwilling to sacrifice lost pay even when unpaid leave is provided (Law Insider Dictionary, 2022). Paid family leave allows mothers and dads to take lengthy periods off work while earning replacement pay, which is a significant difference, especially for lower-income parents who would not otherwise be able to take time off (CEA, 2014).

Performance

The comparison of an organization's aims and objectives with its actual performance in three areas financial performance, market performance, and shareholder value is known as organizational performance. Ali and Qun (2019) feel that items like piloting, assessment, efficiency, effectiveness, and quality should be used to define performance. However, performance is a fluid term that needs some measurement. However, there are many aspects to performance, and in today's corporate world, where profit is king, financial performance is at the top of the list.

Financial performance is a subjective indicator of a company's ability to earn revenue from its principal way of operation. This word is also used as a broad indicator of a company's overall financial health over time, and it may be used to compare similar companies within the same industry or to compare industries or sectors in aggregate (Awaysheh, Heron, Perry and Wilson, 2020).

Employee Performance

Employee performance is intimately linked to the outcomes of one's job in a firm or organization. The work's outcomes might include quality, quantity, and timeliness, but employee growth relies on performance appraisal in the workplace. In theory, performance evaluation is an expression of an employee's performance appraisal form (Irfansyah, 2020). Muhammad (2019) defines performance as "the ability of someone's labour to generate something that fits their capacity." The outcomes accomplished by a person in a field of work according to specified criteria to apply for a certain job and reviewed by certain persons are referred to as performance (Donohoe, 2019).

Components of Employee Performance

The following are components of employee performance reviewed in the study.

Employee Output

In economics, output refers to the amount of products or services produced by a business, industry, or country in a certain time period, whether consumed or utilised for additional production. The output of an organization is the consequence of the usage of inputs in production. Depending on the organization's sector of business, the output might be in the form of services or physical products. Output is described by the Cambridge English Dictionary (2022) as the amount of something produced by a person, machine, industry, or country. Employee output, on the other hand, relates to how much labour one employee can put into the productive process. In theory, a motivated employee is more likely than an uninterested employee to enhance his production (Deardorff, N. D.).

Employee Punctuality

Punctuality tries to ensure that people come to work every day and finish their work hours. Employees that are on time are essential assets to any company that wants to be successful.

Employees who do not adhere to the rules of timeliness are a drain on the system and do not add much to the organization's overall productivity. Managers must guarantee that their staff arrive at the office on time and do not stay late (White, 2012). According to Preethi (2017), timeliness is a trait of responsible employees. It's not just about being punctual. It is an individual's attitude that demonstrates emotional devotion to what they are doing; consequently, it may be characterized as stringent adherence to commitments and promptness.

Employee Retention

Because the competitive advantage derives from the establishment of a loyal workforce, keeping a good employee is crucial for the company (Stewart and Brown, 2011). Organizations that adopt effective retention strategies will not only improve their business, but will also reduce turnover costs, improve productivity and efficiency in the execution of business processes, and boost market access, consistency in customer care, and customer loyalty and retention (Hussain, Taher and Hameed, 2021).

Employee retention is important for an organization's expertise to be preserved. When an employee departs the company, a knowledge void is created. Furthermore, if the turnover of brilliant individuals is substantial, the company will suffer a considerable loss, such as a drop in organizational performance. The reason for this is that replacing cognitive capital through hiring and training is expensive. In order to protect human capital, companies must investigate why people depart and devise employee retention strategies (Chen, 2014).

Conceptual Framework

Fig. 1 Conceptual Linkages of Study Variables

The graphic above depicts the relationships and connections that exist between the study's many individual variables. The graphic depicts the relationship between health insurance and employee production and performance. It also demonstrates how profit sharing affects employee timeliness and, ultimately, employee performance. This is also true of paid time off, which will boost staff retention and, as a result, performance.

Theoretical Framework

The theories reviewed in the study are;

- I. Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory (Henry Maslow, 1943)
- II. Vroom's Expectancy Theory (Vroom, 1964)

The study was also based on Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory, which emphasizes how an individual's needs are hierarchical, with unlocking one level of need allowing place for other levels of need. The first requirements are physical ones, which social security is supposed to address.

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory

Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory, which he devised in 1943, guides the research. According to the notion, people are motivated by strong wants, which are then gratified.

Individuals are inspired to meet their demands at the next level (King-Hill, 2015). Basic needs, psychological requirements, safety needs, love, self-worth, and fulfilment want are Maslow's five categories of human needs. Diet, water, sleep, clothes, and comfort are among the basic categories of human aspirations. The second group includes security and safety requirements, which emphasize danger avoidance, freedom from anxiety, hazard, and deficiency. Societal needs are the third type of desire, and they comprise the requirements for love, belonging, and social connection. The fourth component is self-worth, which includes people's respect and appreciation. Fulfilment and pursuing greater personal growth and involvements are the sixth and final categories. This idea is accepted since salary and other types of social security are required for an employee to meet these demands. To meet fundamental demands, one needed to earn a certain amount of money. As the Maslow hierarchy of requirements progressed, basic salary and compensation were increased to a certain degree in order to provide the person with some financial and working environment stability. An employee is always drawn to a position in which he has a better opportunity of functioning on a high degree of social security. The study is based on this notion in this regard.

Vroom's Expectancy Theory

According to Vroom (1964), individual's demonstration to enlarge expected fulfilment with outcomes is referred to as expectancy theory. According to expectation theory, a person's motivation in a given situation is determined by two factors: (1) the expectation of a link between exertion and a specific result (for example, a specific level of pay for a specific level of execution), referred to as the "exertion result expectancy," and (2) the valence (engaging

quality) of the result. These two components combine to inspire people to choose a degree of effort that they believe will result in the desired outcome.

According to Vroom theory, people behave to increase predicted pleasure with results, and they are motivated by two factors: what they believe the reward is for a certain behaviour (in this case, money) and how much they value that payoff (studies about it shows individuals esteem monetary payoff over non-monetary payoff). Individuals are propelled by a combination of these two factors. People strive when execution-based motives are used, according to Poskela (2009), because they believe they will be rewarded financially if they execute well, and people love money.

Empirical Review

Health Insurance and Employee Output

Owolabi, Ajidagba, Akinola, Falaye, and Irinyemi (2016) used Nigerian Bottling Company Plc. as a case study to examine the influence of health insurance on employee productivity. The study began by assuming that risk and uncertainty are the most important aspects of treatment. The research relies on original data collected using a well-structured questionnaire. A total of 104 questionnaires were distributed to the randomly selected sample from a population of (208). The data was analysed using the person product moment correlation coefficient. According to the findings, there is a considerable link between health insurance and employee productivity. The study found that there is a negative link between risk and uncertainty and health insurance demand ($r = .743^{**}$, $N=104$, $P.01$). There is also a substantial positive correlation between product accessibility and demand for health insurance.

At PT. Kallarent Makassar City, Gunawan, Ilyas, and Naninisih (2018) investigated the impact of labour social security on employee work satisfaction. Primary and secondary data are used in this investigation. The participants in this study were all PT. Makassar Kallarent workers. Data is gathered through observation and interviews. Purposive sampling approach was used to determine the respondents. A single regression analysis was performed. The findings revealed that labour social security had a substantial and beneficial influence on job satisfaction among employees of PT. Kallarent Makassar City, with a high association (correlation) between labour social security and job satisfaction.

At Kenya Tea Packers, Kibet and Kalei (2020) investigated the influence of employee perks on staff productivity (KETEPA). The study looked at previous hypotheses on the subject of the theoretical review, which was Expectancy theory. In addition, the data for the study was acquired from a sample of 286 respondents. The researcher utilized a descriptive study design since it explains all of the activities that take place at KETEPA in great detail. Employee perks have an impact on productivity, according to the research. According to the data, there is a substantial link between employee perks and Kenya Tea Packers Limited productivity (KETEPA).

Profit Sharing and Employee Punctuality

In the example of the Kality foods manufacturing facility, Abebe (2018) looked at the impact of remuneration on staff productivity. Data was collected through a questionnaire, an interview, and a document review. Kality Foods Manufacturing Factory provided the information. The study's overall population is the 368 employees of Kality Foods Manufacturing Factory, and 110 employees were chosen as samples using simple stratified random selection. The data was analysed using descriptive, correlation, and regression analysis. According to the results of descriptive study, all remuneration package factors have an impact on employee productivity. Non-financial remuneration has a negative weak insignificant link with employee productivity, but financial pay has a strong positive significant relationship with employee productivity, according to correlation research. Financial pay has a considerable and positive influence on employee productivity, but non-financial compensation has an insignificant and negative effect on employee productivity, according to the regression analysis results.

Dahkoul (2018) investigated the factors that influence employee performance in the Jordanian industrial sector, especially the impact of employee happiness, management standards, and trainings on employee performance, as well as the mediating effect of employee engagement. As a result, an easy selection method was used to choose a sample of 100 administrative and senior managers from Jordan's industrial sector. Primary data is gathered by sending two questionnaires to each business, one to the administrative manager and the other to the executive management. When using AMOS to accomplish structural equation modelling, a quantitative data analysis approach is used. Employee happiness, management standards, and trainings were shown to be key variables in employee

performance, with a considerable influence on employee engagement, which leads to employee performance. Employee happiness, however, is the most important of the three. Employee happiness, management standards, and training should all be prioritized by organizations in order to improve employee engagement and performance. Mlay (2020) investigated the impact of social security mergers on employee performance in Tanzania, focusing on the public services social security fund (PSSSF). The study used a mixed method approach, which included both qualitative and quantitative methodologies. The sample size was 105 PSSSF respondents who were chosen using random and selective selection approaches. Primary data was gathered through questionnaires and interviews. To present the study's findings, descriptive and inferential statistics were developed. Employee motivation is strong and progressive among employees, with a favourable influence on performance, according to the findings, because they have been assured of job security and all advantages they have been getting from the previous combined firms, as well as more as time goes on. Furthermore, when it comes to the relationship between employee performance and the merger, it is clear that all predicting variables, such as employee commitment, employee involvement, and employee productivity, are all positive and have a statistically significant effect on social security merging ($p < 0.05$). This means that the staff have reacted positively to the merger as a whole, and that high levels of performance are expected.

Paid Leaves and Employee Retention

Employee retention was studied by Shah and Asad (2018) using both intrinsic and extrinsic incentives. In addition, the study looked at the function of perceived organizational support in mediating the motivation-retention link. The commercial banks of Lahore, Pakistan, provided primary data. A total of 342 banking industry personnel from commercial banks in Lahore, Pakistan, were chosen for the study. The data was analysed using partial least squares structural equation modelling. Employee retention is influenced by both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, according to the findings, and perceived organizational support modulates the link between extrinsic and intrinsic drive and employee retention. The research contributes intellectually to Social Exchange Theory, Herzberg Two Factor Theory, and Organizational Support Theory by empirically evaluating them.

The impacts of remuneration on staff turnover in private hospitals in Samburu County were explored by Lekartiwa, Rintari, and Moguche (2020). This study was done in 10 private hospitals in Samburu County using a descriptive survey research approach. Each of the private hospitals in Samburu County provided information through 71 medical practitioners, including senior physicians, senior nurses, senior pharmacists, and senior medical technologists. Each hypothesis was tested using linear regression, and the effects of salary on staff turnover in private hospitals in Samburu County were measured using multiple regression analysis. Tables and extensive explanations were eventually used to present the findings. The study revealed that there was a statistically significant positive association between salary and employee turnover. Simply put, how employees are compensated at the conclusion of their contract or at the end of the month has a significant role in determining whether or not they will quit in the near future. Poor and insensitive pay may likely cause them to depart and seek higher paid opportunities.

In a lighting firm, Soenanta, Akbar, and Sariwula (2020) investigated the impact of work satisfaction and organizational commitment on employee retention. This study employed a quantitative approach with a survey method. The sample size for this study was 204 employees who were chosen at random. Data was collected by questionnaire distribution and evaluated using route analysis. According to the findings, 1) work satisfaction and organizational commitment had a positive direct influence on employee retention, and 2) job satisfaction had a positive direct effect on organizational commitment. The consequence is that poor or strong retention should be considered in corporate management since it affects personnel turnover propensity and resilience.

The influence of employees' retention strategies on organizational memory was investigated by Hussain, Taher, and Hameed (2021). This study is historical, descriptive, and critical in nature. The sample includes 158 faculty members from Baghdad's five private institutions. SEM (Structural Equation Modelling) and SPSS were used to examine the data (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences). According to the findings, the employee retention strategy is critical in keeping people and hence maintaining organizational memory. The findings and suggestions of this study convince private college administrators that staff retention strategies are critical to keeping personnel and hence maintaining organizational memory. This study varies from prior studies in that it focuses on the factors that motivate employees to stay in the business rather than on the factors that motivate them to leave. According to the findings, workers' retention strategies assist the business in retaining its personnel and, as a result, sustaining organizational memory.

Methodology

The area of the study comprised of three (3) selected food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu state. They include: Nigerian Breweries Plc, 9th Mile Corner, Enugu, Aqua Raph Invest. Ltd, 9th Mile corner, opp.Ama Brewries, Juhel Nig. Ltd, 35 Nkwubor Road Emene Pharmaceuticals, table water. The reason for their selection was due to high level of workers, capital base above 20 million naira. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 2668 selected staff of the study institutions. The adequate sample size of three hundred and thirty-six (336) using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. Three hundred and one (301) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 90 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.777 which was also good. Data was presented and analysed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analysed using Z – test statistic tool.

Data Presentation and Analyses

The Effect of Health Insurance on the Employee Output of Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State.

Table 1: Responses on the Effect of Health Insurance on the Employee Output of Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State.

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	Insurance benefits boost employee satisfaction to perform better	1010 202 67.1	44 11 3.7	90 30 10.0	12 6 2.0	52 52 17.3	1208 301 100%	4.01	1.553	Agree
2	Employees place higher value on insurance scheme and it motivates them into action for success.	985 197 65.4	44 11 3.7	90 30 10.0	22 11 3.7	52 52 17.3	1193 301 100%	3.96	1.569	Agree
3	More productivity is enhanced as employees are sure of medical insurance	570 114 37.9	436 109 36.2	66 22 7.3	8 4 1.3	52 52 17.3	1132 301 100%	3.76	1.417	Agree
4	Life insurance of employees make them feel more favourable about their jobs	730 146 48.5	192 48 15.9	126 42 14.0	26 13 4.3	52 52 17.3	1126 301 100%	3.74	1.514	Agree
5	The employees provide good health benefits attracts quality talents.	345 69 22.9	636 159 52.8	54 18 6.0	14 7 2.3	48 48 15.9	1097 301 100%	3.64	1.303	Agree
	Total Grand mean and standard deviation							3.822	1.4712	

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 1 showed that 213 respondents of 301 representing 70.8 Insurance benefits boost employee satisfaction to perform better 4.01 and standard deviation of 1.553 agreed. Employees place higher value on insurance scheme and it motivates them into action for success 208 respondents representing 69.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.96 and standard deviation of 1.569. More productivity is enhanced as employees are sure of medical insurance 223 respondents representing 74.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.76 and standard deviation of 1.417. Life insurance of employees make them feel more favourable about their jobs 194 respondents representing 64.4 percent agreed with mean score of 3.74 and 1.514. The employees provide good health benefits attracts quality talents 228 respondents representing 75.7 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.64 and standard deviation 1.303.

The Influence of Profit Sharing on the Punctuality of the Employees of Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State

Table 2: Responses on the Influence of Profit Sharing on the Punctuality of the Employees of Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	Profit sharing motivates the employee to be on duty	630	388	33	8	52	1111	3.69	1.438	Agree
		126	97	22	4	52	301			
		41.9	32.2	7.3	1.3	17.3	100%			
2	The employee's commitment to the business for the long-term is assured	500	496	36	26	52	1110	3.69	1.417	Agree
		100	124	12	13	52	301			
		33.2	41.2	4.0	4.3	17.3	100%			
3	The addition of profit sharing to other retirement plans promotes absence from duty	385	492	120	18	52	1067	3.54	1.365	Agree
		77	123	40	9	52	301			
		25.6	40.9	13.3	3.0	17.3	100%			
4	Giving workers a portion of a company's profits	320	652	30	14	57	1073	3.56	1.364	Agree
		64	163	10	7	57	301			
		21.3	54.2	3.3	2.3	18.9	100%			
5	A profit share serves as employee retirement plan and it motivates them to be timely and regular.	400	584	54	10	52	1100	3.65	1.354	Agree
		80	146	18	5	52	301			
		26.6	48.5	6.0	1.7	17.3	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.626	1.3876	

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 2 showed that 223 respondents of 301 representing 74.1 Profit sharing motivates the employee to be on duty 3.69 and standard deviation of 1.438 agreed. The employee's commitment to the business for the long-term is assured 224 respondents representing 74.4 percent agreed with mean score of 3.69 and standard deviation of 1.417. The addition of profit sharing to other retirement plans promotes absence from duty 200 respondents representing 66.5 percent agreed with mean score of 3.54 and standard deviation of 1.365. Giving workers a portion of a company's profits 227 respondents representing 75.5 percent agreed with mean score of 3.56 and 1.364. A profit share serves as employee retirement plan and it motivates them to be timely and regular 226 respondents representing 75.1 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.65 and standard deviation 1.354.

The Influence of Paid Leaves on the Employee Retention of Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State.

Table 3: Responses on the Influence of Paid Leaves on the Employee Retention of Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State.

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	Paid leave inspires top talents to work for long term	1010	44	90	12	52	1208	4.01	1.553	Agree
		202	11	30	6	52	301			
		67.1	3.7	10.0	2.0	17.3	100%			
2	The level of productivity is increased as paid boost morale	985	44	90	22	52	1193	3.96	1.569	Agree
		197	11	30	11	52	301			
		65.4	3.7	10.0	3.7	17.3	100%			
3	Providing the benefit of paid time off increases employee happiness and morale.	570	436	66	8	52	1132	3.76	1.417	Agree
		114	109	22	4	52	301			
		37.9	36.2	7.3	1.3	17.3	100%			
4	Offering a competitive benefit package reduces employee finding the grass greener elsewhere	730	192	126	26	52	1126	3.74	1.514	Agree
		146	48	42	13	52	301			
		48.5	15.9	14.0	4.3	17.3	100%			
5	Employee engagement makes them feel valued and reduces turnover costs.	345	628	54	14	50	1091	3.62	1.320	Agree
		69	157	18	7	50	301			
		22.9	52.2	6.0	2.3	16.6	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.81	1.4746	
								8		

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 3 showed that 213 respondents of 301 representing 70.8 Paid leave inspires top talents to work for long term 4.01 and standard deviation of 1.553 agreed. The level of productivity is increased as paid boost morale 208 respondents representing 69.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.96 and standard deviation of 1.569. Providing the benefit of paid time off increases employee happiness and morale 223 respondents representing 74.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.76 and standard deviation of 1.417. Offering a competitive benefit package reduces employee finding the grass greener elsewhere 194 respondents representing 64.4 percent agreed with mean score of 3.74 and 1.514. Employee engagement makes them feel valued and reduces turnover costs 226 respondents representing 71.1 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.62 and standard deviation 1.320.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis one: Health Insurance has No Positive Effect on the Employee Output of Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State.

Table 4: One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Insurance benefits boost employee satisfaction to perform better	Employees place higher value on insurance scheme and it motivates them into action for success.	More productivity is enhanced as employees are sure of medical insurance	Life insurance of employees make them feel more favourable about their jobs	The employees provide good health benefits attracts quality talents.
N		301	301	301	301	301
Uniform Parameters ^a ^b	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.671	.654	.491	.485	.507
	Positive	.173	.173	.173	.173	.159
	Negative	-.671	-.654	-.491	-.485	-.507
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		11.643	11.355	8.516	8.415	8.804
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $8.415 < 11.643$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that health insurance had positive effect on the employee output of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $8.415 < 11.643$ against the critical Z- value of 2.18 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that health insurance has no positive effect on the employee output of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Hypothesis Two: Profit Sharing has No Positive Effect on the Punctuality of the Employees of Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State

Table 5: One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Profit sharing motivates the employee to be on duty	The employee's commitment to the business for the long-term is assured	The addition of profit sharing to other retirement plans promotes absence from duty	Giving workers a portion of a company's profits	A profit share serves as employee retirement plan and it motivates them to be timely and regular.
N		301	301	301	301	301
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.491	.494	.414	.504	.501
	Positive	.173	.173	.173	.189	.173
	Negative	-.491	-.494	-.414	-.504	-.501
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		8.516	8.574	7.190	8.747	8.689
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $7.190 < 8.689$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that the leadership excellence had positive effect on the attendance rate of academic staff of state tertiary institutions in Enugu State.

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $7.190 < 8.689$ against the critical Z- value of 2.18 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that leadership excellence has no positive effect on the attendance rate of academic staff of state tertiary institutions in Enugu State.

Hypothesis Three: Paid Leaves have No Positive Effect on the Employee Retention of Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test						
		Paid leave inspires top talents to work for long term	The level of productivity is increased as paid boost morale	Providing the benefit of paid time off increases employee happiness and morale.	Offering a competitive benefit package reduces employee finding the grass greener elsewhere	Employee engagement makes them feel valued and reduces turnover costs.
N		301	301	301	301	301
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.671	.654	.491	.485	.501
	Positive	.173	.173	.173	.173	.166
	Negative	-.671	-.654	-.491	-.485	-.501
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		11.643	11.355	8.516	8.415	8.689
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $8.415 < 11.643$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that the leadership excellence had positive effect on the attendance rate of academic staff of state tertiary institutions in Enugu State.

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $8.415 < 11.643$ against the critical Z- value of 2.18 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that leadership excellence has no positive effect on the attendance rate of academic staff of state tertiary institutions in Enugu State.

Discussion of Findings

The Effect of Health Insurance on the Employee Output of Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State

The computed Z-value for hypothesis one varies from 8.415 to 11.643 versus the crucial Z-value of 0.000, implying that health insurance had a favourable impact on employee output in Enugu State's food, beverage, and tobacco manufacturing sectors. Owolabi, Ajidagba, Akinola, Falaye, and Irinyemi (2016) used the Nigerian Bottling Company Plc. as a case study to examine the influence of health insurance on employee productivity. According to the findings, there is a strong link between health insurance and employee productivity. The study found that there is a negative link between risk and uncertainty and health insurance demand ($r = .743^{**}$, $N=104$, $P.01$). At PT. Kallarent Makassar

City, Gunawan, Ilyas, and Naninisi (2018) investigated the impact of providing labour social security on employee work satisfaction. The findings revealed that labour social security had a substantial and beneficial influence on job satisfaction among employees of PT. Kallarent Makassar City, with a high association (correlation) between labour social security and job satisfaction. At Kenya Tea Packers, Kibet and Kalei (2020) investigated the influence of employee perks on staff productivity (KETEPA). Employee perks have an impact on productivity, according to the research. According to the data, there is a substantial link between employee perks and Kenya Tea Packers Limited productivity (KETEPA).

The Influence of Profit Sharing on the Punctuality of the Employees of Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State

The computed Z-value for hypothesis two ranged from 7.190 to 8.689, indicating that leadership excellence had a positive influence on the attendance rate of academic staff at state tertiary institutions in Enugu State, compared to the crucial Z-value of 0.000. Abebe (2018) examined the influence of remuneration on employee productivity in the Kality foods manufacturing facility to support the conclusion. Financial pay has a considerable and positive influence on employee productivity, but non-financial compensation has an insignificant and negative effect on employee productivity, according to the regression analysis results. Dahkoul (2018) investigated the factors that influence employee performance in the Jordanian industrial sector, especially the impact of employee happiness, management standards, and trainings on employee performance, as well as the mediating effect of employee engagement. Employee happiness, management standards, and trainings, according to the study, are major elements in employee performance, having a considerable influence on employee engagement, which leads to employee performance. Employee happiness, however, is the most important of the three. Employee happiness, management standards, and training should all be prioritized by organizations in order to improve employee engagement and performance. Mlay (2020) investigated the impact of social security mergers on employee performance in Tanzania, focusing on the public services social security fund (PSSSF). Employee motivation is strong and progressive among employees, with a favourable influence on performance, according to the findings, because they have been assured of job security and all advantages they have been getting from the previous combined firms, as well as more as time goes on. Furthermore, when it comes to the relationship between employee performance and the merger, it is clear that all predicting variables, such as employee commitment, employee involvement, and employee productivity, are all positive and have a statistically significant effect on social security merging ($p < 0.05$). This means that the staff have reacted positively to the merger as a whole, and that high levels of performance are expected.

The Influence of Paid Leaves on the Employee Retention of Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State

The computed Z-value for hypothesis three ranged from 8.415 to 11.643 versus the crucial Z-value of 0.000, implying that leadership excellence had a positive impact on the attendance rate of academic staff at state tertiary institutions in Enugu State. Shah and Asad (2018) researched the impact of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation on employee retention to back up their findings. Employee retention is influenced by both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, according to the findings, and perceived organizational support modulates the link between extrinsic and intrinsic drive and employee retention. The research contributes intellectually to Social Exchange Theory, Herzberg Two Factor Theory, and Organizational Support Theory by empirically evaluating them. The impacts of remuneration on staff turnover in private hospitals in Samburu County were explored by Lekartiwa, Rintari, and Moguche (2020). The study revealed that there was a statistically significant positive association between salary and employee turnover. Simply put, how employees are compensated at the conclusion of their contract or at the end of the month has a significant role in determining whether or not they will quit in the near future. Poor and insensitive pay may likely cause them to depart and seek higher paid opportunities. In a lighting firm, Soenanta, Akbar, and Sariwula (2020) investigated the impact of work satisfaction and organizational commitment on employee retention. According to the findings, 1) work satisfaction and organizational commitment had a positive direct influence on employee retention, and 2) job satisfaction had a positive direct effect on organizational commitment. The influence of employees' retention strategies on organizational memory was investigated by Hussain, Taher, and Hameed (2021). The findings and suggestions of this study convince private college administrators that staff retention strategies are critical to keeping personnel and hence maintaining organizational memory.

Summary of the Findings

- i. Health insurance had positive effect on the employee output of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, $Z(95, n = 301) = 8.415 < 11.643, p < .05$
- ii. Profit sharing had positive effect on the punctuality of the employees of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, $Z(95, n = 301) = 7.190 < 8.689, p < .05$
- iii. Paid leaves had positive effect on the employee retention of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, $Z(95, n = 301) = 8.415 < 11.643, p < .05$

Conclusion

The study found that health insurance, profit sharing, and paid leave had a beneficial impact on employee production, punctuality, and retention in Enugu State's food, beverage, and tobacco manufacturing enterprises. Furthermore, employee performance in an organization fosters productivity because employees who are enthusiastic and deeply rooted in positive attitudes toward the organization and its values are more productive, which is beneficial to the organization and ensures a stronger positive relationship between the organization and its employees. Organizations often try to improve their productivity, which entails achieving their goals and objectives through effective social security.

Recommendation

- i. Manufacturing companies should include health insurance in their employee benefits package since it will help them recruit more qualified employees than those that do not.
- ii. Incentivizing employees encourages them to put in more effort, therefore manufacturing companies may consider including profit sharing among their employee perks to boost employee productivity and satisfaction.
- iii. Paying employees Paid vacation should be promoted to boost employee satisfaction and morale, which will improve staff retention in the long run.

References

- Abebe, H. (2018). Effect of compensation on employee productivity in the case of Kality Foods Manufacturing Factory, Addis Ababa, *M.BA Theses, Addis Ababa Science and Technology University*.
- Ali, M. and Qun, W. (2019). Strategic Management practices and performance of the SMEs in Bangladesh, *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 7(1); 69-78
- Chen, M. (2014). The effect of training on employee retention. *International Conference on Global Economy, Commerce and Service Sciences*, 356-359
- Dahkoul, Z. (2018). The Determinants of Employee Performance in Jordanian Organizations. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Accounting (JEFA)*, 5(1); 11-17
- Dean, Adam (2015). The Gilded Wage: Profit-Sharing Institutions and the Political Economy of Trade. *International Studies Quarterly*, 59(2); 316–329.
- Deardorff, A. (n.d) Output, *Deardorff's Glossary of International Economics*
- Donohoe, A. (2019). *Employee Performance Definition*, retrieved from <https://www.bizfluent.com/facts-7218608-employee-performance-definition.html> (Accessed on the 15th of May 2020)
- Gunawan, H., Ilyas, B. and Naninsih, N. (2018). Effect of labour social security on job satisfaction. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 7(12); 1-15
- Hasibuan, M. S. P. (2013). *Human resource management*. (Revised Edition) Moulds 17, Jakarta: P T. Bumi Script.
- Hussain, A. M., Taher, M. H. and Hameed, M. L. (2021). Employees Retention Strategy and its Impact on Organizational Memory: An Exploratory Research for the opinion of Faculty Members at Private Colleges on Baghdad. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 10(1); 1-15
- Irfansyah. (2020). The Duties and Functions Performance of Aceh Human Resources Improvement Institutions in Scholarship Study Program Implementation in Aceh Government. *Britain International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(1); 160-165.
- Kagan, J. (2021). *Health Insurance*. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/h/healthinsurance.asp>
- Kenton, W. (2021). *Profit-Sharing Plan*. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/p/profitsharingplan.asp>
- Kibet, G. and Kalei, A. (2020). The impact of employee benefits on the employee productivity at Kenya Tea Packers, *International Journal of Management Studies and Social Science Research*, 2(4); 246-254
- King-Hill, S. (2015). Critical analysis of Maslow's hierarchy of need. *The STeP Journal*, 2(4), 54-57.
- Law Insider Dictionary (2022). *Paid leave definition*. Retrieved from <https://www.lawinsider.com/dictionary/paid-leave>
- Lekartiwa, H., Rintari, N. and Moguche, A. (2020). Effects of remuneration on employee turnover in private hospitals in Somburu County, *Human Resource and Leadership Journal*, 5(1); 15-28
- McKay, A. M. (2018). Mean Racial and Ethnic Differences in Sales Performance: The Moderating Role of Diversity Climate. *Personnel Psychology*, 61: 349–374.
- Mlay, E. (2020). Effect of social security merging on employee performance in Tanzania: the case of public service social security fund. *M.BA Dissertation, Mzumber University, Tanzania*
- Muhammad and Hidayat, R. (2019). The Relationship between the Transformational Leadership Style of Madrasah Head and Work Discipline with the Performance of Teachers at MTs N Lima PuluhBatu Bara. *Britain International Journal of Linguistics, Arts and Education Sciences*, 175-182.
- Owolabi, A. O., Ajidagba, A. B., Akinola, A. T., Falaye, F. O. and Irinyemi, B. A. (2016). The impact of health insurance on employees' productivity in an organization in Kwara State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Current Research*, 8(1); 31259-31264
- Pekerti, A., Vuong, Q., Ho, T. and Vuong, T. (2017). Health care payments in Vietnam: patients' quagmire of caring for health versus economic destitution. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 14(10): 1118.
- Poskela, J. (2009). *Management control in the front end of innovation*. Retrieved from <https://www.ijmsssr.org/paper/IJMSSSR00213.pdf>
- Soenanta, A., Akbar, M. and Sariwulan, R. (2020). The effect of job satisfaction and organizational commitment to employee retention in a light company. *Issues in Business Management and Economics*, 8(4); 97-103
- The Council of Economic Advisers (2014). *The economics of paid and unpaid leave*. Retrieved from https://obamawhitehouse.archives.gov/sites/default/files/docs/leave_report_final.pdf

White, L. T. (2012). Is "Punctuality Standard" an Oxymoron?.*Psychology Today*.